

Fresh weight of azolla from insecticide-treated and untreated plots at Sanpahtawng Rice Experiment Station, Cheingmai, Thailand.

months February-May (see figure). Severe insect damage and high summer temperatures caused yields in treated plots to be lower than 6 t/ha. At San-

pahtawng and Sakolnakorn azolla was attacked mostly by a webworm. The key pest at Ubolratchatani was the caseworm. *h*

Changing trends of insect pests of rice in Manipur

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During the past 8-9 years several new insect pests have begun to harm rice in Manipur. Some are spreading to new areas and some that were minor pests are now major pests. Changing trends and their possible causes are discussed below.

Rice leaf butterfly *Melanitis leda ismene*, reported in 1973 in the central district, now infests several high yielding and local varieties in five other hill districts in the state. The pest is more abundant in wetland rainfed conditions where water supply is more or less assured. However, it also infests several local paddy varieties grown in shifting cultivation in dryland rainfed conditions.

The slug caterpillar *Latoia [=Parasa] bicolor* was first noticed in 1980 in cooler regions of East District, Ukhrul. Primary areas of infestation are Kamjong and Phungyar subdivisions, where

several local varieties are monocropped in shifting cultivation in rainfed dryland conditions. The insect is a voracious leaf feeder. It has not been found in other rice belts of the state.

Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* was first found in the warmer Jiribam subdivision adjoining Silchar district of Assam. In 1972, it appeared in cooler areas of Chingai in East District, Ukhrul. By 1973 the pest had reached the central valley of Imphal where 200 acres of paddy grown in rainfed transplanted wetland conditions were infested. The pest is most dominant in Imphal West-I and West-II subdivisions where several high yielding varieties and local varieties are grown.

Rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* attacked large areas of nursery and transplanted paddy at Sowumbung and Sagolmang in Imphal East subdivision in 1975 kharif. It has also been observed in Tengnoupal. Rice fields are susceptible at early tillering stage during long dry spells. Plants grown in dry, poor soils are most often attacked.

Rice leaf miner (prob. *Pseudona-*

pomyza asiatica) was observed in 1973 in the cold area of Mao in the north district. A local dryland variety grown on terraced rainfed fields at an altitude of about 2,000 m was affected. Until 1979 the pest was unknown in other rice growing areas of Manipur. In 1980 it attacked local variety Phouren during early tillering stage at Shamurou in Imphal West-II.

Rice bug *Leptocorisa acuta* is occasionally a serious pest of first crop paddy (Mar-Apr to Jun-Jul) and causes minor damage to the second crop (Jul-Aug to Nov-Dec). The insect is more active in warm, humid conditions at flowering to dough stage. Low temperature at flowering stage during the second crop does not favor insect multiplication.

Rice hairy caterpillar *Psalis pennatula* has been an important rice pest for only 2-3 years. In a few pockets of Tengnoupal district a heavy infestation, sometimes 10-15 caterpillars/hill of Moirang-phou, occurred in July 1982 and caused complete plant defoliation. Sporadic caterpillar infestations are reported during the early monsoon rains.

Changing insect pest trends may be caused by changing cultivation patterns and new agricultural strategies. The area planted to high yielding varieties has increased from 12,000 ha in 1973 to 72,530 ha in 1982. Similarly, the area of minor irrigation in the state increased from 1,700 ha in 1973 to 45,000 ha in 1982. Consumption of NPK rose from 1,820 t in 1973 to 3,000 t in 1982. *h*

Effect of meteorological factors on oviposition and nymphal hatching of, rice tungro virus vector *Nephotettix virescens*

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The effect of meteorological factors on oviposition and nymphal hatching of *Nephotettix virescens*, a vector of rice tungro virus, was studied in the net-house for 2 years. Seeds of Taichung Native 1, Jaya, and IR20 were sown and transplanted in earthen pots at monthly